

What You Say - Appendix A

Appendix A: Reproducibility checklist for authors using WYS in published work

Item 1 — Input provenance

Report the following for each analysis run used in published work: (a) export platform and format (e.g. WhatsApp Android .txt, Telegram .txt); (b) date range of the exported conversation; (c) whether system and event lines were filtered prior to analysis (WYS default: yes); (d) the exact participant handle string entered for resolution, and whether digit-based fallback matching was triggered. If the export was preprocessed or truncated before upload, describe those steps.

Item 2 — Level A configuration

Report: (a) NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon version used; (b) Liberty and MoralStrength resource versions; (c) whether weighted polarity binning was applied for moral framing (triggered when categorical resources are unavailable — note in output); (d) confidence band threshold settings and whether a reliability warning was surfaced; (e) any non-default parameter settings. Current defaults are documented in the repository README and in the commit hash recorded under Item 4.

Item 3 — Level B configuration

Report: (a) model identifier (current default: gpt-4.1-mini - confirm the identifier shown in the run output, as this is environment-configurable); (b) sampling temperature (current default: 0.4); (c) prompt template version or commit hash; (d) input character caps applied to anonymised text excerpt and metric payload. Note that Level B output is non-deterministic - exact wording will vary across calls even with identical inputs. Reproduce the stored levelB_output.json rather than re-running inference for archival purposes.

Item 4 — Run metadata

Report: (a) WYS version or GitHub commit hash at time of analysis (visible in repository; pin the exact commit used); (b) date of run; (c) run identifier if retained. Note that run identifiers are session-scoped and not permanently stored by default - record the identifier at time of analysis if audit traceability is required.

Item 5 — Output archive

Deposit the following files to Zenodo or an equivalent persistent repository and cite the resulting DOI: (a) metrics_levelA.json - the machine-readable Level A output; (b) generated visualisation artifacts (emotion distribution chart, moral loading chart, emoji valence timeline); (c) levelB_output.json - the stored Level B structured output; (d) the GitHub commit hash identifying the exact WYS version used. Do not re-run Level B inference for archival purposes - use the stored JSON from the original run.

Item 6 — Deletion policy applied

Confirm and report: (a) whether immediate deletion (via Delete & Exit) or automatic 24-hour retention cleanup was applied; (b) that no uploaded conversation data or derived artifacts were retained beyond the run; (c) if any deviation from default retention settings was applied, specify the configuration used (see vercel.json in the repository). For published research involving third-party participants, confirm that data handling was consistent with applicable ethical and consent requirements prior to upload.

Availability

WYS is freely available as a web application and as open-source software. All components necessary to reproduce Level A outputs are included in the repository.

Live tool: <https://wys.living-literature.org>

Source code: <https://github.com/RayanBVasse/WhatYouSay>

Zenodo DOI: [to be assigned on upload]

License: MIT

Language: Python (Flask); serverless deployment via Vercel

Dependencies: NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon (Mohammad & Turney, 2010; 2013); Liberty / MoralStrength resources (Araque et al., 2020; 2022); OpenAI API (Level B only)

Tested on: WhatsApp exports (Android and iOS); Telegram and Signal support in beta. Approximately 12–15 chat exports used during development and in Vasse (2026b).